

Table 1. Soil incorporation of fungicides to control ShB on UPLRi 4 under lowland conditions. ^a UPLB, Philippines.

Fungicide	Rate (kg/ha)	Disease severity (%)	Yield ^b (t/ha)
Iprodione 50% WP	1	71.0	4.6 a
Benomyl 50% WP		74.9	4.5 a
Benomyl-EMDOC ^c	1	77.7	4.1 a
Benomyl-iprodione	1	72.9	4.1 a
Triphenyltin acetate 60% WP-triphenyltin hydroxide 50% WP	1	71.8	3.6 a
Triphenyltin acetate iprodione	1	74.8	4.1 a
PCNB	50	87.3	4.3 a
No fungicide (control)	-	90.0	3.7 a

^a Mean of 10 plants/treatment in 3 replications. ^b Sampling area for yield was 1 m². Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^c Ethyl 3-(3-5 dichlorophenyl)-5-methyl-2-4 deoxo-5-oxazolidine carboxylate (Serinal 50% WP).

Table 2. Soil incorporation of controlling ShB on UPLRi 5 under upland conditions. ^a UPLB, Philippines.

Fungicide	Rate (kg/ha)	Disease severity (%)	Yield ^b (t/ha)
Iprodione 50% WP	1	47.0	3.4 a
Benomyl 50% WP	1	50.7	3.1 a
Benomyl-EMDOC ^c	1	44.4	2.1 a
Triphenyltin acetate 60% WP-triphenyltin hydroxide 50% WP	1	48.8	2.9 a
PCNB	50	51.1	2.9 a
No fungicide (control)	-	57.7	2.4 a

^a Mean of 10 plants/treatment in 3 replications. ^b Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 1% level. Sampling area for yield was 1 m². ^c Ethyl 3-(3-5 dichlorophenyl)-5-methyl-2-4 deoxo-5-oxazolidine carboxylate (Serinal 50% WP).

conditions during the 1983 wet season. Varieties were UPLRi 4 for upland and UPLRi 5 for lowland. Upland treatments (six) and lowland (eight) were in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Upland plots measured 2 × 3 m with 20 cm between rows; lowland plots were 2 × 2 m with 20- × 20-cm spacing. Fungicides were incorporated into the plots, and fields were planted the day after treatment. Plants were inoculated 45 d after fungicide application. Rice grain-hull culture of *Rhizoctonia solani* 3-4 wk old was inserted between tillers and between plants. Disease readings were taken 2-3 d before harvest on 10

random plants/plot and severity computed:

$$\text{disease severity} = \frac{\text{sum of disease rating}}{\text{total no. of rating} \times 9} \times 100$$

Under lowland conditions, all treatments except PCNB had significantly less disease than the control (Table 1). Under upland conditions,

Diseases of dry summer rice in eastern Uttar Pradesh, India

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Rice in the eastern part of Uttar Pradesh is mainly grown in the hot wet season 1 Jun-30 Nov. However, some farmers plant a small part of their holdings to rice during the hot dry season 1 Feb-15 Jun. Seedlings are raised while temperatures are still low. Although mainly dependent on irrigation, the crop occasionally receives one or two mild showers. It is harvested before the normal rainy season begins.

We surveyed farmers' fields in different districts and university experimental rice plots at Faizabad for incidence and severity of diseases in 1986 and 1987.

We identified bacterial blight (BB) caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* (Ishiyama) Dye, bacterial leaf streak (BLS) caused by *Xanthomonas*

Incidence and severity of major diseases in hot season rice in eastern U.P., India, 1986-87.

Disease	Disease incidence ^a (%)	Disease score ^b
BB	10-80	3-9
BLS	0-20	1-5
BS	0-20	1-3
Khaira	0-15	2-5
ShB	0-10	1-3
ShR	10-60	5-7

^a Based on percent leaves (BB, BLS, BS), percent culms (ShB, ShR), and percent plants (khaira) infected/unit area. ^b Standard evaluation system for rice, 1980.

plots treated with iprodione and benomyl-EMDOC had significantly less disease than the control (Table 2). In both situations, PCNB had the highest disease rating and disease severity. Iprodione and benomyl, singly or in combination, seem to control disease, although yields did not show significant differences. □

campestris pv. *oryzicola* (Fang et al) Dye, brown spot (BS) caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae* Breda de Haan, khaira induced by Zn deficiency, sheath blight (ShB) caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn, and sheath rot (ShR) caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (Saw.) Gams (see table). Incidence and severity of the diseases varied from cultivar to cultivar and field to field in both years. BB and ShR occurred consistently and, depending on conditions, severely. □

Virulent strain of rice grassy stunt virus (GSV) identified in Indonesia

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An unidentified rice disease showing tungro (RTV)-like symptoms was noticed in Java in 1981. We used a serological assay and transmission test to confirm its causal agent, a virulent strain of GSV.

Latex suspensions sensitized with antisera to GSV, rice tungro bacilliform virus, and rice tungro spherical virus were obtained from IRRI. GSV was detected by the latex test only in leaf samples collected from plants showing RTV-like symptoms at Cianjur, West Java. None of the samples reacted positively to antisera against the RTV-associated viruses.

Laboratory colonies of brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens*